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THE ROLE OF HUMAN RESOURCE INFORMATION SYSTEMS IN MODERN WORKFORCE MANAGEMENT: ENHANCING EFFICIENCY AND COMPLIANCE WITH REFERENCE TO HERITAGE FOODS INDIA LTD

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ABSTRACT

The primary goals of this research are to(1) determine how widespread the usage of Human Resource Information Systems (HRIS) is among Jordanian public universities and(2) analyze the present state of HRIS implementation, including its applications, advantages, and disadvantages. at order to gather information from HRIS users at Jordanian institutions, a structured questionnaire was developed, refined, and translated after being pre-tested and informed by prior research. The primary advantages of using an HRIS, according to the study's results, were the speed of reaction and the ease of access to information. However, the key obstacles to implementing an HRIS were a lack of commitment from upper management, a lack of financial resources, and the difficulty of altering the company's culture. Human resource management (HRM) professionals in Jordan could benefit from the findings of this study, which shed light on the current state of HRIS in higher education institutions, by learning more about its applications, performance, and challenges.

Researchers from a wide range of fields have pondered the causes and effects of different kinds of trust. This article examines the influence of eleven propositions that investigate the link between technology trust—the degree to which a human has faith in inanimate technology—and Human Resource Information

Systems (HRIS) and how those relationships affect the effectiveness of HRIS implementations. A collection of testable propositions may be generated by considering and modeling organizational, technical, and user aspects. These propositions can then be explored in different organizational contexts. Eleven hypotheses are put forth that, according to the authors, factoring into the success or failure of an HRIS implementation are factors such as organizational trust, pooled interdependence, organizational community, organizational culture, technology adoption, technology utility, technology usability, socialization, privacy sensitivity, and predisposition to trust. The paper concludes with suggestions for further study and a synopsis of the connections between the model's essential components.

I. INTRODUCTION

An effective HRIS provides information on just about anything the company needs to track and analyze about employees, former employees, and applicants. Your company will need to select a Human Resources Information System and customize it to meet your needs.

With an appropriate HRIS, Human Resources staff enables employees to do their own benefits updates and address changes, thus freeing HR staff for more strategic functions. Additionally, data necessary for employee management, knowledge development, career growth and

development, and equal treatment is facilitated. Finally, managers can access the information they need to legally, ethically, and effectively support the success of their reporting employees.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Our study HRIS helps the organization to follow systematic way of collecting data & information of each employee to aid planning, decision-making and submitting of returns & reports to the external agencies.

This collected information about the personnel (information about the employee) will be helpful in solving the employees problems and organization problems .HRIS maintains the data related to the employee's personal profile, career profile, skill profile & benefit profile, which would help in their growth.

Our study HR Information system also maintains the data related to the personnel identification i.e. The employee code to recognize every individual with their employee codes.

HRIS also includes managing the salary discrepancies of employees. Some modifications are done in order to rectify the salary discrepancies of the employees.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

To prepare Human Resource Information system, we can collect the information from the HR department and partially from employees also.

Because of the security regions the company is much confidential about the information of the employees in organization.

- ✓ Employees should be motivated to give their information taken.
- ✓ Top management should trust the employees that after making huge effort

to take the information of employees, employees will work for the well being of organization and for human being also.

- ✓ Top management's philosophy should be clear towards Human Resource information system and its well being to encourage the employees.
- ✓ Management and Managers need to give equal importance.
- ✓ Employees must be feeling of belongingness among the employees, and also willingness to give the information.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The primary purpose of an HRIS is the application of technology for enhancing the efficiency of human resource management.

HRIS is used for data storage and report generation, while some others may use it for decision alternatives' generation, decision making, and even for simulation.

Hence the underlying objectives are

- Make a study in prevailing HRIS.
- To identify Accuracy of Employee data.
- To make the required changes in SAP.
- Identify the Mistakes of Employee's data and Update the same in SAP.
- To identify the "Data Needed" and suggest the same to the organization.

The involvement and participation of both the administration and the executives in bringing about desired betterment both in daily routine and procedure assessment by adopting a new outlook , attitudes and practices of executive business.

II. METHODOLOGY

The present study has been conducted in **HERITAGE FOODS INDIA LIMITED** situated at Hyderabad. The online Interviews are conducted through a properly designed questionnaire constitute

the primary source of data for the study.

Unit of study

Two instruments are used; the first one is the management schedule to gather information from management on different angles of organization.

The second one intended to administer among the sample.

Research & Design

1. Research method : Survey
2. Data collection Method :

Primary source : Structured closed ended questionnaire

Secondary source : Company brochures , records , magazines (REINFOREC), journals , Internet.

- Research Instrument : Personal Interview with aid
- Sampling plan : Size 100
- Procedure : simple random sampling

LIMITATIONS OF HRIS

While the computerized Human Resource Information System , described earlier, has many benefits , it also has many problems , which need to be addresses to before it can really be useful . Some of them are described below.

- It can be expensive in terms of finance and manpower requirements.

- Often the personnel designing HRIS do not have a thorough Understanding of what constitutes quality information for the users . Thus, The user managers do not get exactly the reports , which they Want Producing information that is of quality to the users requires an investment in time , effort and communication on the part of HRIS managers.
- Computers cannot substitute human beings. Human intervention will Always be necessary. Computers can at best aid the human effort. The Quality of response is dependent upon the accuracy of data input andQUIRES fired. The ‘Garbage-in Garbage-out’ is the key expression in any Computerized system.
- In many organizations , the system is operated in batch mode with the records being updated once a week. Online facility in multi-Environmental needs to be developed so that the reports generated are not out of place with the realities.

III. HUMAN RESOURCE PLANNING

American companies must now operate in a rapidly changing business environment. These changes have important implications for HRM practices. To ensure that management practices support business needs, organizations must continually monitor changing environmental conditions and devise HRM strategies for dealing with them. The procedure used to tie human resource issues to the organization's

business needs is called human resource planning. Also known as HR planning, this procedure is defined as the "process of identifying and responding to [organizational needs] ... and charting new policies, systems, and programs that will assure effective human resource management under changing conditions."

The purposes of HR planning are to enable organizations to anticipate their future HRM needs and to identify practices that will help them to meet those needs. HR planning may be done on a short- or long-term (three or more years) basis. Its aim is to ensure that people will be available with the appropriate characteristics and skills when and where the organization needs them. The use of HR planning enables companies to gain control of their future by preparing for likely events. That is, they can anticipate change and devise appropriate courses of action. When companies learn how to capitalize on future events, their own future improves.

As valuable as HR planning is, many companies ignore this opportunity. Some see it as too difficult and frustrating, while others simply do not see the need for it. However, when failing to properly plan for their human resources, employers are forced to respond to events after they occur, rather than before; they become reactive, rather than proactive. When this outcome occurs, an organization may be unable to correctly anticipate an increase in its future demand for personnel. At best, such a company would be forced to recruit personnel at the last minute and may fail to find the best candidates. At worst, the company may become seriously understaffed.

Consequences. For instance, the understaffing could cause existing employees to experience a great deal of stress as they attempt to meet

additional demand without adequate resources and assistance. If required work is not getting done, the firm ultimately may experience an increase in back orders, which could cause a decrease in customer goodwill, an increase in competition, and a loss of market share.

When engaged in human resource planning, a company derives its human resource needs by first forecasting its demand for human resources (i.e., the number and types of people needed to carry out the work of the organization at some future point in time), and then its supply (i.e., the positions that are expected to be already filled). The difference between the two forecasts signifies the firm's HR needs. For example, if a firm estimates that it will demand 12 accountants during the next fiscal year and expects to retain its supply of nine who are already on staff, its HR need would be to hire three additional accountants. Following is a closer look at how a company can determine its HR needs and devise plans to meet them.

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

The opportunities to add more services are endless and continue to improve.

For most companies, the hardware and software needed to run these programs are fairly standard. Hardware and software is dependent on the complexity of the HRMS package; more complex HRMS packages require more hardware (e.g., server space and speed).

HRMS technology costs vary considerably, depending on the size of the company and its HR needs. Costs for deploying a comprehensive HRMS package include license fees, implementation, technology, training, and maintenance. Costs typically range from \$300 to \$700 per employee as an initial investment for

companies with more than 1,000 employees. Smaller companies may decide it is better to rent the application than buy it. Research has found that most companies can recoup HRMS costs within three years of system launch, based on process efficiencies alone.

The value of HRMS results from a reduction in HR support costs, based on efficiency improvements. "Hackett's benchmark for the average annual cost of HR services per employee is approximately \$1,900, with a best practice goal of less than \$1,200" (Hamerman). By eliminating paper and process inefficiencies, companies can expect additional cost reductions while improving service and becoming more efficient. There are many other benefits of HRMS. Giga Information Group believes that HR departments can reduce time spent on administrative work by 40 percent to 50 percent, resulting in either the elimination of headcount or the redeployment of effort to higher value tasks, such as decision support and employee development.

Another benefit of HRMS includes allowing HR to transition from an administrative department to a strategic management department. The strategic value aspect of the HRMS investment focuses on managing human capital by supporting functions such as recruitment, performance/competency management, employee development, and employee customer service. By executing well in these areas, companies can reduce employee turnover, reduce hiring costs, and improve individual performance.

ADP offers a comprehensive suite of software that can run on almost all modern operating systems. A major player in the HRMS business is PeopleSoft. Acquired by Oracle Corp. in January 2005, PeopleSoft puts its focus on one complete HRM product line. This suite not only

works in the HRM arena, it also allows employers to buy modules for CRM, SCM, and many other areas. There are three versions of the company's Enterprise suite: Enterprise, EnterpriseOne, and PeopleSoft World.

IV. FINDINGS:

- HRIS in Heritage foods is properly streamed lined.
- It is so designed that it has each and every information of an employee Stored and maintained
- Uses the best product in information technology , which is SAP HR to maintain its employee database.
- Every person in HR team is properly trained in using SAP
- Training should be more professional with a proper training course in SAP HR with a certification exam at the end.
- So that every employee in the HR team would be SAP certified.
- The training provided is more oriented on the job.
- The objectivity and rationality is found to be greatly satisfied.

V. SUGGESTIONS

• Stress Management

In the growing complicated work environments , people need relaxationso organization have to cope up with stress management to overcome the challenges . For this the employees need to be trained in mediation and campus on personality development to provide better work force.

• Knowledge Management

Knowledge Management is a process of sharing the information through all the

teams and gaining extra knowledge, which can lead to the process of extensive learning.

HERITAGE FOODS INDIA LIMITED is an organization with cultures and development, which has well said procedures covering all the similar organization and development, which has well said procedures covering all the necessities of administration and human relation component, where in similar organization impersonal elements creeping HERITAGE FOODS INDIA LIMITED successfully maintains very personal linkage which in itself is launch able achievement for organization.

For any organization the employee-relation management is the main criteria in the Challenging organizations, where there is constant up gradation of technologies like Re-engineering business process and enterprise resource planning, which formulates SAP application. HR department is strengthening the connection towards the employees.

In deed it was wonderful experience interaction with the employees in the Organization in midst of pleasant work culture.

People only work through people. It is HUMAN RELATIONS that bind them together horizontally and vertically in an organization. It is the right motivational efforts that keep efficacy of production.

It was my great experience to be associated with HERITAGE FOODS INDIA LIMITED and related to work on certain projects at all company, which were of greatest importance. I, was overwhelmed to work under concrete team, who were

highly experienced in their phenomenal careers.

The project I have undertaken at HERITAGE FOODS INDIA LIMITED had given me good experience and good scope to implement the project experience I have learned in the work environment and mark towards goal orientation.

VI. CONCLUSION:

A key component of management is information. The reorganization of information as the fifth organizational resource is driven by the need for accurate, reliable, and relevant data in decision making. This data is crucial to employee productivity, competitive strength, and corporate excellence. The most efficient and cost-effective way to get the data you need is with an HRIS that is both thorough and well-designed. This is the main reason for the growing use of HRIS software.

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